

FEMINISM AND THE EXPRESSION OF ITS BASIC FEATURES IN THE NOVELS OF ALICE WALKER

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to provide basic information about the movement of feminism and its main peculiarities reflected in the novels of Alice Walker who is famous feminist writer, poet and activist. Her contributions to American literature is great with her popular, best-seller novels and creative work. Alice Walker undoubtedly occupies a prominent place in the envy of African-American literature. It reflects the struggles and journeys of African American men and women an effort to strengthen and liberate the entire black race. She is associated with the "survival" of her people, who have been discriminated against, humiliated and humiliated by the white American majority. Walker focuses on black women's survival strategies in a racist white society and a patriarchal black society. Her personal experiences and observations as a black woman are repeated in her works and characters. In her creative work, she completely presents that being a black woman is twice as difficult as just being a woman or a black man.

The term "feminism" itself originated in the 1880s in English. In those years, radical feminism emerged, which seeks to strengthen its position in all areas, including sincere women. Society has embraced these ideas that are no coincidence that a phenomenon such as rape has developed in America. Feminist activists are mainly interested in the third world. But overall, society's reaction to the incident is more negative. Over the

decades, many legends about this phenomenon have emerged that need to be broken. Feminism is a woman's business. The main apologist for liberal feminism is John Stuart Mill. This nineteenth-century philosopher is one of the founders of liberal feminism. In his 1869 work, *Obedience to the Woman*, his weak state is a remnant of the past, hindering the development of society. The book did not go unnoticed and became a very important

event. There was a lot of discussion about its content, and the work was immediately translated into many languages, including Russian. The curly-haired women who appeared in the 1870s were read by Mill. But you don't have to be a man who supports women's rights. Feminism seeks to ensure equal rights for people of both sexes. Most of us believe that men and women have equal rights and that patriarchy or matriarchy is inseparable. So we all support feminism.

In protest, feminists are organizing mass bra burning. This colorful history dates back to 1968. American students then protested against the Miss America pageant. At the same time, a sheep was crowned with a joke, and women's magazines like shoes, curls, and corsets were thrown in the trash. To make an impact, the girls wanted to burn their own petrol as well, but gave up the idea because of fire safety. But the idea itself was well received by journalists. So there was an article in the New York Post called "Bra Burners," the headline turned out to be romantic but scary. Thus, the myth of feminist dependence on fiery movements was invented by the media.

Women have been discriminated against throughout human history. The theory of female oppression, which has become the foundation of modern feminism, lies within the framework of a Marxist ideology with oppressed and oppressed classes. Women were classified as oppressed, and there was one who immediately ruled a man. In general, the theory of class struggle shifted from Marxism to the war of the sexes, and many details were copied so precisely. The myth of discrimination against women was

formed in the second half of the 19th century, at the same time as Marx's teaching. Very few people in our time believe this.

Today, women are still discriminated against. There are currently no legal or formal restrictions on discrimination against women in either Western countries or Russia. The standard of living of women is lower. In developed democracies, the life expectancy of women is 6-7 years higher than that of men. It shows who has better living conditions. For example, there are women health centers and programs almost everywhere. But are there many similarities for men? The state spends two to three times more on men's health than men. Labor, criminal, and other laws always include norms that make it easier for women to work or serve their sentences.

Feminism is a system of socio-political movements and ideologies aimed at creating political, economic, personal and social equality between the sexes. Feminism includes the idea that societies prefer men's views and treat women unfairly. To change this, feminism seeks to combat gender stereotypes and create educational and employment opportunities for women that are available to men. Feminist movements work for women's rights, including voting, public office, employment, fair wages and gender inequality, property ownership, education, equal marital rights, and maternity leave.

Feminism refers to an agenda for different beliefs, thoughts, actions, and behaviors. The usual and basic definition of feminism is the belief that women are equal to men and not in the present. It also helps to reduce inconvenience to women,

especially those who are disadvantaged in society, to any organized behavior. Feminism examines the economic, social, political, and cultural diversity of power and rights. Feminism sees sexuality that discriminates and / or oppresses individuals identified as women and does not want such sexuality and implies its improvement or elimination. Feminism sees people who believe that men have an advantage in the reproductive system, as well as that sex is harmful to men. "Am I not a woman? Is it a black woman and feminism?"

The main similarities between those who use terms for their beliefs, ideas, actions, and movements are:

A. Feminism consists of culture-like ideas and beliefs for women when compared to things like the world because women are only men. In a moral sense, this form or aspect of feminism is a descriptive trait. According to the assumptions in feminism, women are not treated equally with men and women are uncomfortable compared to men.

B. Feminism also includes ideas and beliefs about what culture should and should be - vulnerabilities, ideals, revelations. From an ethical point of view, this form or aspect of feminism is rigid.

C. Feminism includes ideas and beliefs about the importance and significance of the transition from A to B.

D. Feminism also refers to a set of groups and individuals who are committed to organized action, which involves changing the behavior of individuals involved in the action and persuading others outside the action to make the change. In other words, feminism describes a culture that differs from men because women are feminine,

and this difference falls on the position of women in treatment; feminism considers such treatment to be cultural and therefore can change not only "whatever the world may be"; feminism, as far as possible, looks at another culture and the values that correspond to that culture; and feminism is about activism, both individually and in groups, that makes personal and social changes more relevant to the desired culture.

There are many differences in ideas and groups and categories of movements called "feminism": This is considered injustice, discrimination or oppression Is the status of women in culture produced by women and should a patriarchal society exist, disappear, be questioned and destroyed? Sexuality is expressed as conscious and unconscious personal attitudes and behaviors, and how do individuals maintain sexual morality even when they are not consciously or unconsciously having sex? Will the goal be equal treatment and opportunities for women and men to achieve in similar areas of work and culture, or will it have equal respect in different roles? Which women's experiences are different from women of different races, classes, age groups, etc.? How important is the significant differentiation of inequality towards women or the importance of women? Feminism has crossed different economic and political beliefs and created different paths of feminism. Among them socialist feminism, Marxist feminism, liberal feminism, bourgeois feminism, individual feminism, cultural feminism, social feminism, radical feminism, ecofeminism, and so on.

Feminism emphasizes that men have certain benefits of sexuality, and that these benefits disappear when they achieve feminist goals. Feminism usually benefits from men's real interactions and self-awareness, which allows them to achieve these goals. Origin of the word Although it is common to see the word "feminism" used for figures such as Mary Wollstonecraft (1759 - 1797), the word was not that early. The term appeared as *féminisme* in French in the 1870s, although it was speculation used earlier. At the same time, the word refers to the freedom or liberty of women. Hubertine Auclert used the term working in 1882 as a definition of individuals to liberate herself and other women. The 1892 Congress in Paris was described as "feminist." In the 1890s, the term began to be used in 1894 in Great Britain and then in America.

Walker was the first black woman to win the award (351; 352- 57). That same year, Walker's novel also won the National Book Award (Walker xiv; 21). In response to the awards, Walker delayed the case honoring the joy his heroes felt, he just seemed so to care for the wide recognition of the people who motivated her work and valued (White 358-61). The novel has sold more than six million copies, and Walker, who was indeed formed, refused to attend the Pulitzer Festival In New York (White 362-63; World Changed 21). In Search of Our Mothers' Gardens, published six months later (1983) Color Purple sold very well after the Pulitzer Prize (White 370). The book, which consists of short parts, focuses on black women to other black women, black community and themselves (White 373). The title essay further develops the research It is a literary theory

of black women, like the Welsh course (White 373-78). Walker was featured in the New York Times cover story "Novel author Alice Walker: Telling the Story of a Black Woman" (White 380-81).

Alice Walker's novels focus on women's rights, rules, equalities between men and women. One of his best novel is Meridian is also about feminism' basic features that they lasted more than fifteen years, beginning in 1954 Until 1968 in America. It was definitely one The biggest riots in American society, as well The lives of blacks in America. Harakat freed blacks from open divorce, and made them real American citizens feeling. After the move, of course, the blacks Jim-Crow came out of the teeth of the laws and Terrible conditions that weakened them centuries. Walker talked about it The importance of the civil rights movement essay "Civil Rights Movement: What Was it good? In its search text Gardens of Our Mothers: Female Prose (1984). He said: "Civil rights The movement is deadly only for the white media. In the above in the collection of essays Walker observes The move was a great boon for the black American society because it united blacks America and forced them to seek their own legitimacy rights. She speaks of it as action victories, quasi victories, and landmark minutes.

Walker emphasizes movement united the black community in her novel. This gave life to the blacks who were Saddened by the plight of America. There is a walker applauding the move, "If knowing my condition is all freedom I am take it from the "freedom movement," which is better ignorance, forgetfulness and frustration, similar existence the existence of the animal. As Walker said, Civil Rights

The movement informed blacks in America their condition, and to seek them and they are free from their "secondary" status". Walker imagined the novel there can be real change in black society only society itself happens social and psychological changes. The novel once again emphasizes the importance of the woman participate in black color change Society through the meridian character Hill, the female protagonist of the novel. Walker which is the focus of the novel, the type of leadership that can really lead a positive change for the black community. Dag Mc Adam is in the political process and Development of the Black Uprising (1930-1970) described leadership as "its own source." conditioned by the degree of availability an organization within the affected population."

In conclusion, Walker's novels are about the journey of black women to integrity. Female characters grow as they move from positions of weakness to positions of relative strength. The protagonists 'understanding of the past is so important to their personal change now and that they can change in the future, Walker emphasized, and thought to achieve integrity. Walker's masculine characters achieve psychological health and integrity only if they are able to recognize women's pain and their significance in it. Her works are composed of individuals striving for self-expression, leading to self-empowerment. In her personal life, Walker

went from an eight-year-old girl with a scar on his right eye to a young teenager who had an early abortion, sat with suicidal thoughts, and then came to life as an active participant in life. The civil rights movement and marriage to a white Jew, the search for originality in her mother's gardens, the expansion of her worldview, his attitude toward women, and her personal growth as a poet and as a writer who talks about the woman who appeared in him.

In short, Walker's novels end with the rescue of the heroes. Each key character carries out recovery in a unique way, taking into account differences in circumstances and social environment. Alice Walker, as an activist and writer, seeks to create an understanding between the organization through her work. Although she is an African-American woman, she knows the suffering of the entire black community. She tries to remember the past so that humanity realizes its mistake and creates equality between them. So, feminism is the most crucial movement and the main idea in the political branch of society that is based on protection of women's rights, rules, roles in the family, society and other fields. Nowadays famous activist, feminist writer Alice Walker is still working and writing on the women's issues in order to give much more opportunities to all women by her great actions in the society and creative work.

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